

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.13291902
Version : 1
Publication : August 2024
Type : Preprint

Mini Review: The Waste Threat in the Cilamaya Kulon Mangrove Forest, Karawang, Indonesia

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Citation :
Aini, B. M. N., & Taofiqurohman, A. (2024). Mini Review: The Waste Threat in the Cilamaya Kulon Mangrove Forest, Karawang, Indonesia. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13291902>

Abstract

Karawang Regency, located on the North Coast of West Java, Indonesia, covers an area of 1,753.27 km² with a population of approximately 2.37 million people as of 2022. The region's geography includes a diverse range of landscapes, from hilly areas to coastal plains, with a coastline stretching 84.23 kilometers. The coastal areas, including mangrove ecosystems, play a crucial role in environmental stability, serving as protective barriers against coastal erosion, flooding, and strong winds. Mangroves also contribute to carbon sequestration and serve as vital habitats for various marine and terrestrial species. However, these ecosystems face significant threats from anthropogenic activities, particularly the disposal of waste. Plastic waste, in particular, poses a severe risk to the mangrove ecosystems by obstructing the flow of oxygen and water, leading to vegetation death. The increase in waste, exacerbated by tourism and urban activities, highlights the need for effective waste management strategies to protect these valuable coastal ecosystems. The multifaceted value of mangroves—ecological, economic, and socio-cultural—underscores their importance in maintaining the environmental balance in Karawang and the broader region.

Keywords : Waste, Mangrove, Karawang

Introduction

Karawang is a plain area geographically located at coordinates 107°02' - 107°40' East Longitude and 5°56' - 6°34' South Latitude, with an altitude of 0 - 1,279 below sea level, with areas ranging from hilly areas to coastal areas (Karawang Fisheries Service, 2013). Karawang Regency is one of the areas located on the North Coast of West Java which has a coastline of 84.23 kilometers, so it has a gentle coastal relief, there are many deltas, and includes inter-island waters, Karawang waters in this case directly border the Java Sea so that the dynamics of the coast are influenced by waves originating from the Java Sea (Pasaribu et al., 2019; Sulma et al., 2013).

Figure 2. Administrative Map of Karawang
Source: (Karawang Fisheries Service, 2017)

The area of Karawang is 1,753.27 km², according to data from the Central Statistics Agency (2022), in 2022 the total population of Karawang reached 2,370,000 people. The borders of the Karawang region, to the east it borders Subang, Bekasi borders to the west of Karawang, Purwakarta borders to the southeast, Bogor borders to the south, and the Java Sea borders directly to the north (Karawang Fisheries Service, 2017). According to administrative data, the Karawang Coast consists of 9 sub-districts with 25 villages in them, namely the sub-districts of Tempuran, Cilebar, Pakisjaya, Batujaya, Pedes, Tempuran, Cibuaya, Tirtajaya, Cilamaya Kulon and Cilamaya Wetan.

Figure 3. Administrative Map of Karawang Coastal Area
(Source : Komarudin, 2013)

As a coast that has the second longest coastal area in West Java, the Karawang coast has quite large potential in terms of land use, including agriculture, aquaculture, protected forests, and mangrove forests. The distribution of mangroves in Karawang is

spread across nine Pesisir Karawang sub-districts with the largest rows of mangrove forests in five sub-districts, namely Cibuaya, Pakisjaya, Batujaya, Tirtajaya, Cilamaya Kulon and Cilamaya Wetan (Pasaribu et al., 2022). Based on BPS Data in 2021, Karawang Regency has two mangrove tourist attractions, namely the Sedari Mangrove Forest in Cibuaya District and the Pasir Putih PRPM Mangrove Tourism in Cilamaya Kulon District. Cilamaya Kulon is the northernmost coastal area of Karawang before Cilamaya Wetan and Subang Regency. Cilamaya Kulon and Cilamaya Wetan are the lowest areas on the Karawang Coast, with a wavy contour (Komarudin, 2013). Cilamaya Kulon has two coastal villages, namely Sukajaya Village and Pasirjaya Village. Pasirjaya Village has a coastline of 0.9 kilometers with a mangrove forest area of 5 ha and a potential area of non-vegetated mangroves of 37.98 ha, while the length of the Sukajaya Village coastline is 3.6 kilometers, with a mangrove forest area of 25 ha, and a potential area of non-vegetated mangroves of 8.29 ha (Karawang Environmental Service, 2018). Cilamaya Kulon, Karawang is always visited by many local and out-of-town tourists. Anthropogenic factors can cause degradation in the mangrove ecosystem and change the composition of the mangrove cover (Majid, 2016). The behavior of tourists and local communities at the PRPM Cilamaya Kulon Tourism, Karawang can bring potential threats and damage to the mangrove ecosystem. The impact of tourists' carelessness results in damage and even death to mangroves, so that mangroves can no longer function as a shelter for biota and a place for biota to find food (feeding ground). Apart from that, mangroves function as a place to breed young fish (nursery ground) and as a place to spawn biota (spawning ground) (Gunarto, 2004; Hara, 2009; Majid, 2016).

The aim of writing the article above is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the mangrove ecosystem on the coast of Karawang, West Java, including its ecological, economic and socio-cultural potential, as well as the various threats it faces. This article also focuses on the importance of mangroves in stabilizing the coastal environment, their function as habitat for various types of biota, and their contribution to climate change mitigation through carbon sequestration. In addition, this article highlights the problem of waste, especially plastic waste, which poses a serious threat to the sustainability of mangrove ecosystems and coastal environments in general. This article aims to increase awareness about the importance of mangrove conservation and the negative impacts that human activities can have on this ecosystem.

Mangrove Ecosystem

Mangrove ecosystem is an ecosystem that is included in the coastal ecosystem with vegetation types that grow and develop in the transitional areas of sea and land, along the coast in tidal areas and river estuaries, so that mangroves are greatly influenced by tides (Tarigan, 2008; Muharam, 2014; Kurniawan & Pribadi, 2014). Mangroves grow in tropical and subtropical climates in intertidal areas of mud, sand, or clay, need to be inundated by water but not all the time, can be inundated every day or inundated at high tide at night, so mangroves require inundation (Bengen, 2001; Prihadi et al., 2018; Pasaribu et al., 2022).

Figure 4. Mangrove Ecosystem in the Intertidal Zone

Mangroves generally grow in intertidal and subtidal areas so that they are protected from the effects of large waves and winds, strong tidal currents, and can live in brackish water areas with not so high salinity. Therefore, mangroves are often found in bay areas, shallow waters, estuaries, deltas, and areas with protected beaches (Kennish, 1990). Sufficient freshwater input also greatly affects the growth of mangroves, so mangroves need to grow near river mouths. Areas with strong waves and tidal currents make it difficult for mangroves to survive, this is because mangroves require substrate and mud sedimentation to grow and develop, so most mangrove forests are in shallow waters with calm water (Dahuri, 2001).

Mangroves are flowering plants with complex root systems, substrate conditions with thick mud and are included in anaerobic (Tomlinson, 1994; Muharam, 2014). The complex mangrove root system is able to stabilize the mud substrate by binding the mud substrate. Indicators of a body of water can also be seen from mangroves, mangrove roots can reduce hazardous metal waste and pollutants, to make the water quality of a body of water clean (Retnowati et al., 2017). In addition, mangroves play a role in absorbing carbon in the issue of global warming. The process of photosynthesis in mangroves can absorb inorganic carbon and then convert it into organic carbon which is formed in its root system, and the results of this organic material do not rot, but the carbon in mangrove forests is five times more than the carbon capacity in tropical forests.

Figure 5. Carbon Cycle in Mangroves (Tomlinson, 1986)

Mangrove forests are a combined ecosystem of land and sea components. Mangroves function as a connector and balancer of the two ecosystems, where flora and fauna live interdependently with nutrients flowing through the mangroves (ZAMRONI & ROHYANI, 2008). The mangrove ecosystem as a gateway to the coastal ecosystem has quite important multifunctions in terms of ecology, economy, and socio-cultural aspects (Wibowo & Handayani, 2006). The important value of mangroves in terms of the physical aspects of mangroves is as a stabilizer of coastal areas, maintaining sediment and substrate stability, protecting the coastline from flooding, abrasion and coastal erosion, protecting the coast from large waves, preventing sea intrusion into land, and protecting settlements from strong winds (Gunarto, 2004; Prihadi et al., 2018; Matatula et al., 2019; Fikri et al., 2021).

The ecological potential of mangroves is the role of mangroves in supplying nutrients and organic materials, in this case the fall of mangrove leaf litter is organic material that can be used as food for microorganisms, organic materials that have been destroyed will become food for crustaceans, worms, bivalves, and gastropods that live in the mangrove area (Pramudji, 2000; Muharam, 2014) so that mangroves act as a place to find food for biota (feeding ground), mangroves as nutrient providers, a place to breed young fish (nursery ground), as a place to spawn biota (spawning ground) (Bengen, 2001; Gunarto, 2004; Hara, 2009; Eddy et al., 2016), as a place to live and shelter birds, mammals, and wildlife (Ezwardi et al., 2009; Majid, 2016). The existence of biota in the mangrove ecosystem that makes holes as their residence underground is important for soil aeration and leaching of salts in the mangrove ecosystem, so that mangroves are useful as a barrier against seawater intrusion into the land (Muharam, 2014).

Mangroves have an economic factor by being a livelihood for coastal residents, such as providing fish, shrimp, and crabs that can be sold and provide high economic value, or by utilizing mangrove parts such as mangrove wood which can be used as furniture materials (Putri et al., 2021). In addition, other non-wood parts of the mangrove can also be utilized, other mangrove products such as honey, can be used as medicines, dodol, and others (Kusmana, 1995). Meanwhile, the socio-cultural potential of the mangrove ecosystem, namely the mangrove ecosystem can be used as a cultural development area or as a tourist attraction, and as an Education-Based Conservation Area (Wahyuni et al., 2015) Mangrove forest areas that are used as tourism objects, can not only be used as education-based conservation areas, but can also help the economy of the surrounding community who live in coastal areas. Tourist attractions in the mangrove ecosystem include trekking, bird watching, fishing, boating, and mangrove planting activities (Wahyuni, 2006).

Threats to Mangrove Ecosystems

Mangroves have economic factors that have high economic value, but are very vulnerable and easily affected by pressure and threats, especially if there is a change in the environment. The mangrove ecosystem is in an open space with open access properties unlike coral reefs and seagrass so that humans can easily exploit and damage it (Eddy et al., 2019; Wibowo and Handayani 2006). Threats to the mangrove ecosystem can come from various things, namely anthropogenic threats and natural threats (Eddy et al., 2016). These threats and pressures can cause degradation of the area of mangrove cover. Waste is the remains of human activities that are considered useless or in the form of useless natural processes. As stated in Law No. 18 of 2008 concerning Waste Management, waste is the remains of human activities in the form of any activity that produces waste in the form of solids, liquids, emissions, and/or natural processes in the

form of organic and inorganic substances, can be decomposed or cannot be decomposed, and is considered to have no value that is thrown into an environment (Artiningsih, 2008; Ginting, 2017).

Population density affects the production of large amounts of waste. The population in coastal areas affects the increase in waste production around coastal areas. Daily human activities will not be separated from producing waste products in the form of waste, garbage, or pollutants. Then, it is stated in the Environmental Law No. 32 of 2009 article 1 (14) that pollution is a substance, living creature, or energy, or other components that are entered or enter an environment that can cause a decrease in environmental quality because it is considered to have exceeded the established quality standards. There are many types of waste in the environment, namely wet waste (garbage) comes from household waste that is easy to rot, such as leftover food or vegetables that are easy to rot and release liquids that cause odor but can be decomposed by microbes, in this case it means it is biodegradable and classified as organic waste. Inorganic waste comes from non-biological materials or from manufactured materials, which cannot rot or rot (refuse), and cannot be recycled into other materials (Astuti, 2010). This type of waste cannot rot naturally for years, for example glass, metal, paper, ceramics, mica, and plastic waste, and waste that can rot slowly, such as wood (Gelbert et al., 1996) in Artiningsih, 2008. B3 waste is waste in the form of liquid waste that is dangerous to health and the environment and is difficult to decompose by microbes. If waste is not sorted properly, it will result in pollution that will harm the soil, water and air (Salim, 2010).

According to (Gelbert et al., 1996) in Artiningsih, 2008 and (Dainur, 1995) waste comes from various sources, and some of the waste that is often found generally comes from various human activities such as:

- a. Household waste
Household activities in residential areas will always produce waste in the form of wet waste or organic waste, household waste from the kitchen, food scraps, fruit peels, vegetables, and sanitary waste (diapers, sanitary napkins, tissues).
- b. Waste from trading activities
Waste produced by stalls or shops, including leftover food waste, plastic food packaging waste, unsold vegetable waste, and others.
- c. Industrial waste
Industrial waste produced in the form of waste water, waste dust, leftover raw materials, leftover building materials, and leftover semi-finished materials, etc.
- d. Livestock Waste
Waste produced by animals and plants in gardens and farms, including, for example, waste from gardens, rice fields, and pens, in the form of food waste (straw, corn stalks, rice stalks), broken twigs, vegetable waste, fertilizer waste, animal waste, animal carcasses, and plant insecticide waste.
- e. Fishery or pond waste
Waste generated from fishery or pond cultivation activities, including fish feed waste, fish carcasses, and others.
- f. Tourism activity waste
Waste generated by tourism activities, both in coastal and mountainous areas, is generally in the form of plastic waste, organic waste in the form of wood or broken twigs, and sanitary waste.

Organic waste can be a natural food for biota living in waters, but if the amount of organic waste is uncontrolled in a body of water, it will reduce the oxygen content in the water. For example, the liquid produced by waste will make the waters full of organic acids

in the form of methane, causing an unpleasant odor. Meanwhile, inorganic waste such as plastic waste can block sunlight from entering the waters, so that natural processes that require sunlight such as photosynthesis will be disrupted. Both organic and non-organic waste are equally detrimental and can disrupt the aquatic ecosystem.

Indonesia is the country that contributes the second largest amount of plastic waste in the world, as reported by the Indonesian Plastic Industry Association (INAPLAS) and the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), Indonesia contributes 64 million tons/year of total waste with 3.2 million tons of plastic waste dumped into the ocean (Yusuf, 2019). The increasing population of Indonesia will increase the volume of waste every second, various types of waste produced in every human activity make waste continue to increase, producing an average of at least one kilogram of waste per day per person with a total of 220,000 tons of waste per day in the national range (Ngoc & Schnitzer, 2009; Ginting, 2017). The use of plastic has become a daily necessity for human activities ranging from household needs to commercial needs in trade. Plastic is made from synthetic polymer base materials that are processed through this polymerization process into a very popular material among the public (Asia & Arifin, 2017), even in the last 50 years the use of plastic has increased 20 times.

Figure 6. Trash in coastal ecosystems (Personal Documentation)

Waste in coastal areas does not entirely come from the coast, but comes from human activities that originate from river flows downstream and end up on the coast carried by currents or waves. Generally, waste that is often found in coastal areas is plastic waste and sanitary waste, such as plastic food packaging, plastic bags, styrofoam, sacks, ropes, cans, drink bottles, used diapers, and others. The waste from the use of plastic used by urban communities will always end up in coastal ecosystems (Patuwo et al., 2020), not only from urban areas but sources of waste can also come from tourism and beach recreation activities, so that waste can be categorized as an anthropogenic threat that has a negative impact on coastal ecosystems (Ginting, 2017.; Patuwo et al., 2020). Plastic

waste has properties that are very difficult to decompose for a very long time, so it can damage and even cause death in coastal ecosystems. The death of coastal vegetation, especially mangroves, is due to piles of plastic waste from tourism activities. Waste blocks the supply of oxygen and water, causing mangrove vegetation to have difficulty breathing (Eddy et al., 2019; Michel & Fingas, 2016).

Conclusion

Karawang, a plain area in West Java, has a coastline of 84.23 kilometers and a population of 2,370,000. The region is home to a diverse range of land use, including agriculture, aquaculture, protected forests, and mangrove forests. The mangrove ecosystem in Karawang is spread across nine sub-districts, with the largest rows in five sub-districts. Two mangrove tourist attractions, Sedari Mangrove Forest and Pasir Putih PRPM Mangrove Tourism, are located in the region. Mangroves are vital for stabilizing the coastal environment, providing habitat for various biota, and contributing to climate change mitigation through carbon sequestration. They are found in bay areas, shallow waters, estuaries, deltas, and areas with protected beaches. However, human activities, such as pollution, can cause degradation and damage to the mangrove ecosystem. Proper waste sorting and management are essential to protect the mangrove ecosystem and its inhabitants. Indonesia contributes the second largest amount of plastic waste globally, with 64 million tons of waste annually.

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